

CLOSING GAPS IN WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

FINDINGS FROM AFRICA AND SOUTH ASIA
EEG APPLIED RESEARCH PROGRAMME GRANT

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WHY FOCUS ON GENDER GAPS?

Enhance Development Outcomes

Moral Imperative

Risk Management

WORLD BANK FOCUS ON GENDER AND ENERGY: 6 REGIONS, 94 COUNTRIES

GLOBAL PROGRAMS

Data and Policy

Women in STEM

Clean Cooking and Heating

Gender and Geothermal

Energy Efficiency, Gender and Behavior Change

Off-Grid Toolkit

WHAT DO WE KNOW ABOUT GENDER GAPS IN THE ENERGY SECTOR?

- 1) Research on gender in the power sector is a new area, with many data gaps. Most estimates put the average percentage of women in the power sector at 22-25% of total employees (World Economic Forum), with significant differences between regions and companies.
- 2) Research by IRENA and others shows **higher percentages of women in renewables** (32%) than the rest of the sector (IRENA 2019).
- 3) Research on the impact of gender quotas is mixed, but the countries with the highest percentage of women employees have quotas (Iceland, Norway).
- 4) Research by USAID and others shows high degrees of **gender segregation** within electric utilities—women commonly work in finance, human relations, legal and accounting departments (USAID 2015 and World Bank 2019).
- 5) Research shows a **correlation** between business performance and gender diversity in the workplace, including in the energy sector:
 - Companies with more women chairs on the board returned a 36% higher return on equity than those with none (MCSI 2015)
 - Study of 200 largest utilities revealed energy companies with greater gender diversity on the board and in management yielded a higher return on equity (E&Y 2016).

HOW ENERGY COMPARES TO OTHER SECTORS

Women's Share of Workforce, by Infrastructure Industry

Industry group	CEO	Board members	Senior roles	Mid-level roles	Junior roles	Lines roles	Staff roles
Industries Overall	9%	28%	15%	24%	33%	30%	35%
Basic and Infrastructure	2%	35%	9%	13%	22%	14%	20%
Energy	0%	32%	11%	19%	24%	19%	22%
Information and Communication technology	5%	19%	11%	21%	32%	23%	33%
Mobility	9%	17%	13%	21%	28%	25%	34%

WOMEN OCCUPY FEW LEADERSHIP POSITIONS

WHY ARE THERE SO FEW WOMEN WORKING IN THE ENERGY SECTOR?

Barriers to Women's Employment

Societal

- Laws may prohibit certain types of employment
- Biased social norms and expectations
- Child care/home responsibilities → less time and/or mobility
- Fewer women in STEM pipeline
- Few/no role models

Institutional

- Lack of adequate facilities/equipment for women
- Sexual harassment
- Gender bias in recruitment and promotion processes
- Lack of internship/training opportunities
- Lack of leadership commitment
- Resistance to change

EEG RESEARCH GRANT

Objective: Identify successful strategies for narrowing employment gaps between men and women

Focus: Power Sector Institutions

Two Regions, Two Implementation Approaches

South Asia: Regional network targeting women professionals in eight countries, focus on engineers and STEM

Africa: Country-specific focus, research tied to identifying gaps and assessing measures taken to address them

EEG GRANT: METHODOLOGY

Eliminating Data Gaps

Qualitative Data Collection

- Key informant interviews
- Focus groups

Quantitative Data Collection

- Sex-disaggregated data
- Baseline survey on employment and gender policies

Stakeholder Mapping

- Energy companies
- Government
- Academia
- Donors
- Non-profits

- Identify gender gaps
- Inform interventions
- Monitor results
- Develop best practices/success stories
- Share knowledge

WHAT WE HAVE LEARNED IN SOUTH ASIA: EMPLOYMENT

8 Baseline Assessments on Women's Representation in South Asia Region Power Sector: Data collected from over 100 energy and academic institutions. Over 500 women and men contributed through focus-group discussions and key informant interviews.

- **Women as % of overall staff: 3-22%**
- **<1-16% women in technical positions**

WHAT WE HAVE LEARNED IN SOUTH ASIA: ACADEMIA/STEM

Female engineering faculty:
0%

Female engineering faculty:
17% (7/42)

Female engineering faculty:
15% (203/1,376)

Female engineering faculty:
15% (30/192)

Female engineering faculty:
4% (3/68)

Female engineering faculty:
6% (11 IIT - 36/326)
 National 2018 - 1.15/4.019 million
 (28%) female B.S. engineering

Female engineering faculty:
0%

Female engineering faculty:
21% (27/126)

Note: Includes electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, power systems engineering and civil engineering programs. Faculty count includes visiting lecturers, teaching assistants and technical support staff.

Female Representation in Engineering Programs is Low:

- Women enrolled in engineering degrees: **0-23%**
- Female Engineering Faculty: **0-21%**

OUR SOLUTION: WePOWER

What is WePOWER?

A **Regional Professional Network** designed to address barriers to women's employment identified in the qualitative research:

- Lack of **female role models and mentors** for students and professional women in STEM
- Limited **networking opportunities** for women in STEM
- Limited exposure to new ideas and desire for **professional development**
- HR policies and physical facilities that are not always **gender friendly**

WePOWER will:

- Support higher **participation** of women in the energy sector and utilities
- Foster higher **retention and professional development** of women in the energy sector
- Promote **normative change** regarding women and girls in STEM

WePOWER Partners implement gender activities under 5 pillars

WEPOWER ACTIVITIES AND TARGETS UNTIL 2020

****WePOWER has 21 Partners – of which 10 are major public and private power utilities in the SAR region**

WHAT ARE WE DOING IN AFRICA?

- Conducted review of energy projects across Africa portfolio
- Selected three pilot countries for research focus: Ethiopia, Kenya and Zambia
- Respond to gender gaps and opportunities identified by Africa Energy Program
 - Research to narrow data gaps and inform implementation
 - Integrate women's employment initiatives into World Bank lending programs
 - Knowledge sharing and dissemination

WHAT WE HAVE LEARNED IN AFRICA: EMPLOYMENT

- Baseline survey tool piloted with three energy companies in Kenya and Ethiopia
- On average, **women make up 21% of the workforce in the companies surveyed**—higher than in South Asia, but slightly below the global average of 22-25%
- **Women made up 14% of technical employees** (range of 7-20%)
- The data confirms the existence of **occupational segregation** by position, with most women working in non-technical positions.

Female Staff by Position

WHAT WE HAVE LEARNED SO FAR IN AFRICA: COMPANY POLICIES

- All energy companies had non-discrimination policies
- All energy companies had anti-harassment policies with grievance mechanisms in place
- Flexible work options generally are not available
- Childcare options are limited
- All energy companies had gender committees with focal points, but not all staff were aware of them
- Mentoring programs are limited or non-existent (for men and women)

ETHIOPIA ELECTRIC UTILITY: BOLSTERING RECRUITMENT AND RETENTION

In \$375 million World Bank funded Ethiopia Electrification Program \$4.5 million is set aside for gender, including:

- Construction or renovation of childcare facilities in headquarters and 11 regional offices
- GBV prevention and response
- Career development and leadership training for women in STEM:
 - MoU signed with universities/Ministry of Science for internship and scholarship program
 - Internships for 40 female students in STEM/year
 - Full scholarships for 44 current female staff (Masters)/year
 - Short-term professional development training for 55 women/year (50% STEM areas)
 - Mentorship program for 52 emerging female leaders/year

KENYA POWER AND LIGHTING CO LTD: ENSURING SUPPLY OF TECHNICALLY SKILLED WOMEN

- WB Project in Approval Phase – **Kenya Electricity System Improvement Project**
- Addresses two gaps identified in gender assessment:
 - lack of women in STEM pipeline
 - tuition is barrier to female enrollment for relevant degrees/training
- Project to include a scholarship program for **60 women** at the Institute of Energy Studies and Research
 - **Craft Certificate in Electrical Engineering (2 years)**
 - **Diploma in Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, and ICT (3 years)**
- Scholarship recipients will receive support during training – including internships, mentors and coaching.

IN THE WOMEN'S OWN WORDS: KENYA TVET STUDENT FOCUS GROUP

Q: Why are you studying to become an electrical technician?

"I want to prove that I can do it. Anything a man can do, a woman can do better."

"I have passion for this career, and my skills will be marketable, especially as a woman."

Q: What did your friends say when you told them you'd chosen to enroll?

"They said I must be smart, because it would be so hard."

THANK YOU!

GLOBAL

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REGIONAL

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EAP | Helle Buchhave

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